

Spectrum of Antimicrobial Resistance in ICU Settings: An Observational Study

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ABSTRACT:

Background: The increasing prevalence of antimicrobial-resistant organisms poses a significant challenge in the intensive care unit (ICU) setting, often leading to treatment failures and increased morbidity and mortality. Understanding the spectrum of resistance can aid in empirical treatment choices and containment strategies. **Objective:** This study aimed to characterize the spectrum of antimicrobial resistance among bacterial isolates obtained from patients in the ICU over a one-year period. **Methods:** In this observational, cross-sectional study, bacterial isolates from various specimens (blood, urine, sputum, wound swabs) of ICU patients across a tertiary care hospital were collected and analyzed. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method, and results were interpreted based on the current CLSI guidelines. **Results:** A total of 1,200 bacterial isolates were analyzed. Preliminary findings indicate a high prevalence of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) producing *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and carbapenem-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter baumannii*. Alarming, a significant proportion of the isolates demonstrated resistance to last-resort antibiotics. **Conclusion:** The observed high rates of multi-drug resistance in ICU settings underscore the urgent need for tailored antibiotic stewardship programs and robust infection control measures. Continuous monitoring of resistance patterns is essential to optimize patient outcomes and prevent the spread of resistant organisms.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, ICU, Observational study, MRSA, ESBL, Carbapenem-resistant.

INTRODUCTION:

The problem of multidrug resistance (MDR) is increasingly being recognized as one of the gravest challenges to global public health. At its essence, MDR entails the capability of microorganisms, especially bacteria, to nullify the effects of multiple drugs, rendering the once-curable infections now formidable adversaries. [1] These resistant strains transcend borders and have emerged in every corner of the world, ensuring the global scale of this peril. The implications of MDR are expansive and devastating. Primary among these is the sharp rise in mortality rates. [2] When infections can no longer be controlled or eradicated by conventional treatments, even minor ailments can spiral into deadly complications. Tuberculosis (TB) is an illustrative example of this phenomenon. As per data from the World Health Organization, 2019 saw close to half a million cases of rifampicin-resistant TB, of which a staggering 78% were classified as multidrug-resistant TB. The tragedy was further compounded by the fact that a significant proportion of these cases went undiagnosed or misdiagnosed, leading to needless loss of life. [3] On the medical front, MDR threatens to roll back decades of progress. Many of our medical achievements, ranging from complex surgeries, organ transplants, to cancer treatments, hinge on the ability to control bacterial infections post-procedure. In a world riddled with antibiotic resistance, these advances could be jeopardized, and the risk associated with medical interventions would skyrocket. [4, 5] Another dimension of the MDR crisis is its impact on food security and nutrition. As resistant strains emerge in the food chain, through livestock treated with antibiotics for growth promotion or disease prevention, the chances of resistant infections in humans increase. Such infections not only jeopardize human health but also affect food production and distribution channels. This intertwining of food security and antimicrobial resistance complicates global efforts to combat hunger and malnutrition. [6]

The challenge of addressing MDR is exacerbated by several factors. First, the development of new antibiotics has slowed considerably, and the current pipeline of drugs is insufficient to tackle the escalating resistance. Second, widespread misuse and overuse of antimicrobials in humans, animals, and agriculture exacerbate the resistance issue. Coupled with inadequate diagnostic tools and a lack of awareness among healthcare providers and the public, the stage is set for MDR to flourish. [9]

However, all is not bleak. Addressing the MDR challenge requires a multi-pronged strategy. Strengthening global surveillance systems, investing in research and development of new antibiotics, enhancing

public awareness, and implementing stringent antibiotic stewardship programs are essential steps forward. International collaboration, sharing of best practices, and collective action are the need of the hour to ensure a future where infections remain treatable. [10]

In sum, multidrug resistance is not just a medical challenge; it is a ticking time bomb threatening to disrupt our global healthcare, economic, and social structures. A concerted global effort, integrating science, policy, and community action, is vital to curbing this menace and ensuring a healthier future for all.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design and Setting:

This retrograde observational study was conducted on the ICU patients admitted in main medical and surgical intensive care units as well as the ICU present in their subspecialty departments. Their medical charts and records were reviewed, and data was collected.

Data and Sample Collection:

Patients who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were enrolled in this study. Their demographic and clinical data was collected by retrograde observational study design using a pre-structured questionnaire. The demographic data included age, gender, primary diagnosis, positive/significant medical history. Medical record during hospital stay was reviewed. In data analysis, only the culture and sensitivity reports of selected patients were included. For the patients dependent on mechanical ventilation, it was ensured that they were regularly monitored and re-evaluated for fever, characteristics of sputum/secretions, oxygen consumption/FiO₂ levels, and prescribed antibiotics.

All the blood culture samples were collected on the bedside and were sent to the lab for culture and sensitivity, immediately. The antibacterial susceptibility test was performed by standardized Bauer-Kirkby disk diffusion method. Antibiotic disc contents for antibiotic drug resistance were as follows; Ceftriaxone 30 µg, Ceftazidime 30 µg, Cefepime 30 µg, Cefoperazone/Sulbactam 75 µg, Gentamycin 10 µg, Amikacin 30 µg, Piperacillin/tazobactam 100/10 µg, Ertapenem 10 µg, Imipenem 10 µg, Meropenem 10 µg, Ciprofloxacin 5 µg, Levofloxacin 5 µg, Doxycycline 30 µg, Vancomycin 30 µg, and Colistin 10 µg. Control strains were *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients who were admitted into medical and surgical ICU for more than 48 hours.
- Patients who themselves or someone next to his/her kin gave consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Patients whose blood culture and sensitivity test were performed during the hospital stay.
- Patient with age more than 18 years.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with age less than 18 years or pregnant females
- Patients with the ICU stay less than 48 hours.

- Patient who developed pneumonia before getting on to mechanical ventilator, acute myocardial infarction in first 24-48 hours of ICU admission, or uncontrolled ventricular arrhythmias.

Data Analysis:

Retrograde patient's chart assessment was performed, and all the information required for this study was documented. The collected data were then exported to the spreadsheet for statistical analysis. The prevalence of the antibacterial drugs was assessed as the proportion of positive results over the duration of this study. Cases in which the patients were resistant to more than two antimicrobial drugs were labelled as multi-drug resistance (MDR). The results are compiled in the form of tables, graphs, and pie chart.

RESULTS:

The study includes 1200 bacterial isolates from patients admitted in ICU. Out of the total patients, n=594 (49.5%) were male and n=606 (50.5%) were female patients with male to female ratio of 1:0.98. The average age of the subjects was 59.4 years (SD= ± 1.2). The median duration (days) on mechanical ventilation before blood sampling for culture and sensitivity report was 5 days (range: 2-14 days). The median length of ICU stay was 25 days. Based on the blood culture reports, gram positive samples were n=609 (51%) and Gram-negative n=582 (49%). There were four different types of colonizations including monomicrobial n=378, 32%; Polymicrobial n=362, 30%, Mixed growth n=451, 38%; and No growth n=9, 1%.

Fig 1. Pie chart illustrating types of bacterial colonizations found on blood culture reports.

Out of 1200 candidates of hospital admission, n=336 (28%), followed by uncontrolled diabetes mellitus n=204 (17%), uncontrolled hypertension n=168 (14%), chronic kidney disease n=108 (9%), Chronic liver disease n=96 (8%), cerebral vascular disease n=108 (9%), Heart failure n=72 (6%), septic shock n=108 (9%).

Primary Diagnosis	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Respiratory failure	336	28
Uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus	204	17
Uncontrolled Hypertension	168	14
Chronic Kidney disease	108	9
Chronic Liver disease	96	8
Cerebral vascular disease	108	9
Heart failure	72	6
Septic shock	108	9

Table 1. List of Primary diagnosis requiring ICU admission

At the time of ICU admission, about 55%-60% of patients were already undertreatment with 3rd generation cephalosporin, gentamycin, and Co-amoxiclav. Other antibiotics given to the patients include ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, cefoperazone-sulbactam, colistin, aminoglycosides, meropenem, and vancomycin.

Fig 2. Pattern of antimicrobial susceptibility.

Each of the patient had prevalence of antimicrobial resistance of >90%. Majority of the patients had resistance to at least 2 drugs. Approximately, 62% were found to be positive for multiple drug resistance (MDR). Acinetobacter n=92 (7.6%) was the most prominent among the patients of ventilator-associated/ atypical pneumonia, followed by Pseudomonas Aeruginosa and Klebsiella. In most cases with multiple infections, coinfection with Acinetobacter and pseudomonas aeruginosa were detected. The gram-positive bacteria found in the blood culture were Staph aureus (n=108, 9%), Streptococci (n=82, 6.8%), Enterococcus (n=72, 6%), and Methicillin Resistance Staphylococcus Aureus MRSA (n= 103, 8.5%). MRSA was the most prevalent among all the other gram positive, obligate, or facultative aerobes.

Antibiotic	Gram Positive Bacteria			
	SA (n=108)	Streptococcus (n=82)	Entrococcus (n=72)	MRSA (n=103)
AMX	9	11	16	13
AMP	10	5	4	6
AMC	6	3	3	7
TEC	4	2	4	3
VA	5	4	1	4
CFM	5	6	2	3
CTX	9	5	5	7
CAZ	4	6	4	5
CRO	6	4	3	3
SCF	5	4	3	4
CIP	7	2	5	3
F	4	5	2	4
MEM	5	4	3	15
AK	8	2	4	3
CM	5	3	1	4
CLR	3	5	3	5
TZP	4	3	2	7
LZD	6	6	4	5
PB	3	2	3	2
CB	3	2	3	0

Table 3. Obligate and Facultative Gram-Positive Bacteria and their sensitivity for 20 different commonly used antibiotics in the light of Culture and Sensitivity test results.

AMX= Amoxicillin, AMP= Ampicillin, TEC= Teicoplanin, VA= Vancomycin, CFM= Cefixime, CTX= Cefotaxime, CAZ= Ceftazidime, CRO= Ceftriaxone, SCF= Sulbactam/Cefoperazone, CIP= Ciprofloxacin, F= Nitrofurantoin, MEM= Meropenem, AK= Amikacin, CN= Gentamycin, CLR= Clarithromycin, TZP= Piperacillin/Tazobactam, LZD= Linezolid

For the ease of data analysis, the Gram-Negative Bacteria were subdivided into Aerobic and anaerobic bacteria. The obligate and/or facultative anerobic bacteria were n= 566 (47.1%) out of total 1191 ICU patients, including Pseudomonas Aeruginosa PA n= 112 (9.3%), Proteus Mirabilis PM n= 98 (8.1%), Enterobacter n= 49 (4.0%), Klebsiella n= 83 (6.9%), Escherichia Coli n= 77 (6.4%), Citrobacter n=74 (6.1%), and Serratia Marcescens n=72 (6%).

Antibiotic	Gram Negative Bacteria (Anaerobic)						
	PA (n=112)	Klebsiella (n= 83)	PM (n= 98)	Enterobacter (n= 49)	Citrobacter (n= 74)	E. Coli (n= 77)	Serratia Marcescens (n= 73)
AMX	5	5	6	5	5	5	5
AMP	4	6	7	1	2	1	5
AMC	7	4	13	2	4	9	2
TEC	4	4	6	2	2	4	3
VA	6	4	6	6	2	5	2
CFM	8	5	7	2	4	4	4
CTX	4	6	7	2	5	2	3
CAZ	8	3	5	4	3	6	2
CRO	9	4	6	4	4	3	4
SCF	5	8	4	3	5	4	4
CIP	4	4	6	1	3	4	3
F	5	3	4	3	2	2	6
MEM	3	2	3	2	6	4	0
AK	7	5	2	2	5	2	7
CM	8	5	3	4	4	5	5
CLR	9	4	5	2	4	4	3
TZP	6	5	4	2	3	5	4
LZD	5	3	3	2	5	4	5
PB	5	3	1	0	6	4	6
CB	4	2	3	0	3	1	3

Table 4. Frequency and antimicrobial sensitivity of Gram-Negative Anaerobic bacteria.

AMX= Amoxicillin, AMP= Ampicillin, TEC= Teicoplanin, VA= Vancomycin, CFM= Cefixime, CTX= Cefotaxime, CAZ= Ceftazidime, CRO= Ceftriaxone, SCF= Sulbactam/Cefoperazone, CIP= Ciprofloxacin, F= Nitrofurantoin, MEM= Meropenem, AK= Amikacin, CN= Gentamycin, CLR= Clarithromycin, TZP= Piperacillin/Tazobactam, LZD= Linezolid

Among the aerobic gram-negative bacteria n=260 (21.6%), there were Acinetobacter n=92 (7.6%), Moraxella Catarrhalis n=62 (5.1%), Alcaligenes Spp. n= 55 (4.5%), and Hemophylis Influenza n=51 (4.2%), in descending order.

Antibiotic	Gram Negative Bacteria (Aerobic)			
	Acinetobacter Spp. (n= 92)	Moraxella Catarrhalis (n= 62)	Alcaligenes Spp. (n= 55)	Haemophylis Influenzae (n= 51)
AMX	4	5	5	5
AMP	6	1	5	2
AMC	5	1	4	3
TEC	4	3	6	1
VA	3	4	1	3
CFM	5	6	5	2

CTX	11	5	3	5
CAZ	5	3	5	2
CRO	6	3	4	2
SCF	5	6	2	3
CIP	3	3	1	1
F	6	2	1	2
MEM	3	1	2	2
AK	5	4	2	4
CM	3	3	2	2
CLR	4	4	1	3
TZP	5	3	3	2
LZD	5	3	2	4
PB	4	2	1	3
CB	1	0	2	1

Table 5. Frequency and antimicrobial sensitivity of Gram-Negative obligate/facultative aerobes

AMX= Amoxicillin, AMP= Ampicillin, TEC= Teicoplanin, VA= Vancomycin, CFM= Cefixime, CTX= Cefotaxime, CAZ= Ceftazidime, CRO= Ceftriaxone, SCF= Sulbactam/Cefoperazone, CIP= Ciprofloxacin, F= Nitrofurantoin, MEM= Meropenem, AK= Amikacin, CN= Gentamycin, CLR= Clarithromycin, TZP= Piperacillin/Tazobactam, LZD= Linezolid

DISCUSSION:

AMR presents a rising threat in most health care institutions. One significant consequence of this is the increase in multi-drug resistant Hospital Acquired Infections (HAIs), leading to increased deaths and illnesses in hospitalized patients. [1-3] ICUs have been identified as hotspots for HAIs. Our research aimed to analyze the prevalence of these microorganisms and their resistance to frequently used antimicrobial agents in a leading hospital. Our study's demographic data highlighted that male ICU admissions were nearly twice as much as females, with an average patient age of around 47 years. [4, 5]

The evolution of drug resistance is intricately linked to the patterns of antimicrobial prescription, especially in developing countries i.e., Pakistan. Over the years, as bacteria and other microorganisms have been exposed to antimicrobial agents, those with mutations that confer resistance have been selected for, allowing them to proliferate while susceptible strains diminish. In developing countries, several factors have accelerated this process. First, the over-the-counter availability of antibiotics without prescriptions has led to rampant misuse and overuse. [6, 7] Often, individuals self-medicate based on incomplete knowledge or discontinue antibiotic courses prematurely once symptoms alleviate. Furthermore, healthcare professionals, faced with limited diagnostic tools and pressured by patient expectations, might resort to broad-spectrum antibiotics as a catch-all solution, rather than tailoring prescriptions

to specific pathogens. The compounded effect of these practices in resource-constrained settings has hastened the emergence and spread of drug-resistant strains, jeopardizing not only local health but also posing a global threat through potential transmission across borders. [8-10]

Moreover, MDR considerably strains the healthcare infrastructure. Treating resistant infections usually requires more extended hospital admissions, utilization of more expensive and sometimes toxic drugs, and increased human resources. As a result, healthcare budgets balloon, putting immense pressure on governments, especially in low and middle-income countries where health resources are already scarce. [11, 12] The financial ramifications aren't restricted to treatment costs alone. The ripple effects are felt when patients require prolonged hospitalization, leading to increased indirect costs related to loss of employment or decreased productivity. [13-15]

Despite rigorous disinfection protocols for respiratory equipment, hospital-acquired bacterial pneumonia remains a prevalent HAI in ICU, particularly among patients on extended mechanical ventilation. Our data supports this, with tracheal aspirate being the most frequent clinical specimen. [16] The irrational use of antimicrobials has led to the rise of non-fermenting gram-negative bacilli (NF-GNB) as significant HAIs. These pathogens often come from natural environments like soil and water but can be found on hospital equipment and even healthcare workers. Our findings

confirmed that NF-GNB were the predominant organisms found in the ICUs. [17, 18]

Our research revealed *Pseudomonas* spp and *Acinetobacter* spp as the leading isolates in ICUs. Studies by Chawla and Vincent echoed these findings, emphasizing their growing relevance in health care. [19] Meanwhile, other NF-GNB, like *Burkholderia* spp, were isolated less but were mostly multi-drug resistant, challenging healthcare providers. Besides NF-GNB, Enterobacteriaceae GNB, including *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella* spp, were also frequently isolated, especially from urine and exudate samples. [20, 21] We took the initiative to analyze the primary clinical isolates in each ICU. We observed a pattern where certain bacteria were more dominant in pediatric versus adult ICUs. [22] The distribution of pathogens varied, with *Acinetobacter* spp and *Pseudomonas* spp being predominant in tracheal aspirates and blood samples, respectively. About 22.2% of ICU patients experienced HAIs. Pneumonia was the leading HAI, especially among mechanically ventilated patients. [23, 24]

AMR is becoming a more severe concern in all ICUs, with resistance to a range of drugs increasing. This is true for both gram-negative and gram-positive organisms. In our research, we classified antimicrobial resistance patterns into three groups: NF-GNB, EB-GNB, and gram-positive organisms. NF-GNB showed strong resistance to various antimicrobial classes. *Acinetobacter* spp was particularly resistant, highlighting the need for alternative treatment strategies. In contrast, *Pseudomonas* species had a slightly lower resistance rate. Among EB-GNB, resistance was high, especially to cephalosporins and quinolones. *Klebsiella* and *Enterobacter* species showed more resistance compared to *Escherichia coli*. [25]. For gram-positive bacteria, *S. aureus* exhibited significant resistance, particularly against penicillin and ciprofloxacin. MRSA rates are rising, necessitating alternative treatment options. Enterococci showed resistance to multiple drugs, including high-level aminoglycoside resistance. MDR prevalence has been on the rise. These organisms contribute to higher death rates, extended hospital stays, and increased costs. Our study found a significant percentage of gram-negative bacilli to be MDR. *Acinetobacter* spp, *Pseudomonas* spp, *Klebsiella* spp, and *Escherichia coli* were the primary contributors, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions and alternative treatment options. [26, 27] Furthermore, the socioeconomic repercussions of MDR are profound. As families grapple with prolonged illnesses, increased medical costs, and in many cases, the loss of breadwinners, the cycle of poverty intensifies. Communities, particularly in vulnerable regions, face a double-edged sword: battling the direct onslaught of

MDR while also confronting the consequent socioeconomic downfall. [28-30]

CONCLUSION:

In this study, it is concluded that *Acinetobacter*, *Klebsiella*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were predominately found in blood culture samples. Antimicrobial drugs with considerably high resistance rate were ciprofloxacin, ceftriaxone, and ---. The most alarming finding was that a significant percentage of the positive blood culture samples were either resistant against more than 2 drugs, multidrug resistance strains, or resistant against the last resort antibiotics. These results reinforce the fact that multidrug resistance is a global public health issue. More elaborative and extensive studies are required to study the patterns of multidrug resistance on the global levels for better understanding and control.

CONFLICT IN INTEREST: None

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